

FAIR – CARE – Open

FAIR Principles, CARE Principles and Open Data – what are the differences?

- ❖ **FAIR, CARE, and Open Data** offer competing, but complementary visions for making digital outputs accessible. Each stresses different types of data, different communities, and/ or offers a different rationale for doing so.
- ❖ The **FAIR Guiding Principles** for scientific data management and stewardship (Wilkinson et al. 2016) mandate that digital research objects be **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable**, providing “a set of minimal guiding principles and practices for research data stewardship in the life sciences” (Boeckhout et al. 2018). They express the idea that scientific data should be human- and machine readable (ibid.), describing a philosophy for managing digital research objects (Wilkinson et al. 2018).
- ❖ The **Open Data movement** seeks to apply the principles of openness and accessibility to a wider class of digital objects: government data, scientific data, and various types of public and private sector information (Huijboom & Van den Broek, 2011), to improve democratic governance and participation (Dawes et al. 2016: 15). Against the increasing privatization and commercialization of knowledge (Janssen, 2012), the open data movement holds that data should be **Accessible, Transparent, Reusable, and Timely**.
- ❖ Concerns about data reuse and sharing embodied in open and FAIR data have neglected the tensions in protecting indigenous rights and interests in indigenous data versus supporting open data, machine learning, data sharing, and big data initiatives (Carroll et al. 2020; Cole et al. 2023). **The CARE Principles (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics)** promote equitable participation in processes of data re-use (Carroll et al. 2020). In this, the three sets of principles are complementary, each stressing different aspects of data sharing (FAIR = interoperability, CARE = equity & data ownership, Open = transparency).

	FAIR Principles	CARE Principles	Open Data
Applies to	All scholarly outputs (data, code, etc.)	Indigenous data	Government data, scientific data and various types of public and private sector information
Aims	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure that digital research objects can be discovered and reused • Reduce barriers to data discoverability and reusability • Render digital research objects „machine actionable“ (Jacobsen et al. 2020) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support indigenous self-determination/ sovereignty • Support open data (sharing), machine learning, and big data • Stress (collective) data ownership and collective data control • Strengthen collective rights and interests • Strengthen indigenous languages/ worldviews/ capabilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase transparency and accountability of governance • Foster Innovation and Economic Growth • Improve Decision/ Policy-Making • Increase Engagement/ Participation • Improve Efficiency/ Service Delivery
Target Audience	(Machines), Researchers, Research Funders, RPOs, Research Support Staff, Policymakers, interested publica	Indigenous (collective) data holders/subjects	Data producers (public/private)
Challenges and Limitations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adoption • Funding/ Financial sustainability • Interoperability/Standards • Community-specific data practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adoption • Implementation/ Protection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Quality and Reliability • Privacy and Security Concerns • Sustainability and Funding • Engagement and Adoption • Technical Barriers and Interoperability